

DETERMINATION OF PRE-SCHOOL TEACHERS' COMPETENCES TO PREPARE CHILDREN TO LITERACYⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of the current study is to determine pre-school teachers' competences in developing works to prepare children for literacy. The current study, aiming to determine pre-school teachers' competences in developing works to prepare children for literacy, employed the phenomenological design, one of the qualitative research methods. The study was conducted with the participation of 18 pre-school teachers working in pre-school institutions. The data of the current study were collected with a semi-structured interview form and an observation chart developed by the researcher. In the analysis of the data, the descriptive analysis technique was used. As a result of the current study it was concluded that the pre-school teachers conduct limited variety of activities within the context of preparing children for literacy, they mostly prefer desks to conduct these activities, they prefer teacher-centered activities and they experience some problems during the process in relation to parents, children and provision of materials.

Keywords: early childhood, literacy, preschool teachers', competences

1. Introduction

Quality literacy preparation works offered during the pre-school period, which is the most basic step of education, can raise students' interest in literacy; thus, make important contributions to their development in the way of being good readers and writers. Before learning reading and writing, children acquire information, skills and attitudes in relation to this process. Through these preparatory information and skills, they can have more positive experiences during the literacy process they will undergo

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when they start elementary school. However, the children not having prior experiences to prepare for this literacy process can encounter many challenging situations. Moreover, quality literacy preparation works play an important role in children's developing positive attitudes towards reading and writing and gaining reading habit.

In the relevant literature, skills of preparation for literacy are sequenced in different ways; however, all of these skills show their impact in different stages of literacy development process. Phonemic awareness, vocabulary, visual perception, spelling recognition, alphabet knowledge, listening and speaking literacy are the basic literacy preparation skills. Phonemic awareness is defined as the ability of disintegrating a word into its syllables and phonemes and manipulating individual sounds (phonemes). In other words, phonemic awareness refers to awareness of phonemes in spoken language (Schnobrich, 2009). According to Yangın, Erdoğan and Erdoğan (2010), for children to develop their phonemic awareness, they need to be aware of the fact that words can have rhymes, which they can start with the same phoneme and end with the same phoneme and that sentences are made up of words and words are made up of syllables.

Another field that should be fostered within the context of preparing for literacy is to develop children's vocabulary. Vocabulary development is a life-long process (Rupley and Nichols, 2005). The pre-school period is also critical in the development of visual perception skills. Skills developing in this period come to full maturity until the child becomes nine years old and approximate the ones possessed by an adult until the age of twelve (Tsai, Wilson and Wu; 2008). The existing research has emphasized that visual perception training offered at early ages will have positive effects on children's reading maturity, eye-motor perception development and academic skills (Akaroğlu and Dereli, 2012; Sanghavi and Kelkar, 2005; Navah, Orit, Shifra and Yehiela, 2009; Yüksel, 2009).

During the pre-school period, children are expected to acquire writing-oriented skills such as eye-hand coordination, recognizing the meaning of writing, knowing how to hold a book and how to turn pages, recognizing the direction of reading, recognizing capital letters and lower case letters, knowing how to hold a pencil properly and paying attention to written elements around (Justice, Skibbe, Canning, 2005; Erdoğan, 2013).

Listening and speaking are other important skills to be addressed within the context of preparation works for literacy during the pre-school period. Before children start reading-writing, they have already enrolled in the language acquisition process through listening and speaking. In the pre-school period, children gain most of the knowledge they have by means of listening. In addition, children can express themselves by conveying this knowledge to others through speaking (Erdoğan and Erdoğan, 2010).

Given the importance of opportunities provided for children at early ages in the acquisition of these skills, the significance of quality education given in pre-school institutions becomes evident. Teacher competences certainly play an important role for the successful rendering of these works in pre-school institutions. Research focusing on the role of the teacher in inculcating literacy skills has emphasized that the teacher'

knowledge, attitude and behavior about literacy and opportunities provided by the teacher to nurture children's literacy skills can positively affect the acquisition of these skills by children. According to Çakmak and Yılmaz (2009), teachers' level of awareness of the importance of reading consciousness and of the works directed to preparing students for literacy is an important element affecting the development of children in literacy. In pre-school institutions, the teachers who have the habit and consciousness of reading and who are competent in conducting works to prepare children for literacy can provide environments and conduct suitable activities for children to develop literacy skills, positive attitudes and behaviors so that these children can more easily gain the habit of reading. In this regard, determination of teachers' opinions and practices in relation to works to be done to prepare children for literacy is of great importance.

Ergül, Karaman, Akoğlu, Tufan, Sarıca and Kudret (2014) investigated the pre-school teachers' level of knowledge about the concept of early literacy through the interviews conducted with the teachers and observed in-class activities done within the context of early literacy and made some evaluations on the basis of these interviews and observations. As a result of this study, it was concluded that the teachers do not have enough knowledge and their in-class practices are not good enough to support children's development.

In a study conducted in Turkey to determine the pre-school teachers' self-efficacy perceptions of conducting works to prepare children for literacy, it was found that the teachers see themselves as highly competent. Moreover, with increasing years of teaching experience, their self-efficacy perceptions were also found to be increasing (Bay, 2008).

In another study conducted to investigate the works done by the pre-school teachers to prepare children for literacy through interviews, it was found that the teachers are aware of the importance of works directed to preparing children for literacy in terms of the children's self-confidence, their level of readiness for elementary school and muscle development. However, the teachers were found to be mostly using photocopies, workbooks and drawing activities to prepare children for literacy (Dönmezler, 2016).

Teachers' attitudes, behaviors and perceptions in relation to preparation for literacy and the opportunities they provide for children to develop their literacy can have considerable effects on the development of these skills by children. In this regard, teachers should try to create a classroom environment rich in written materials for children, to encourage children to interact with reading and writing materials, to equip themselves with scientific book reading methods and to inform families about how to support their children's early literacy skills. However, teachers' practices directed to developing literacy preparation skills may vary. In this connection, the purpose of the current study is to determine pre-school teachers' competences in developing works to prepare children for literacy.

2. Method

The current study, aiming to determine pre-school teachers' competences in developing works to prepare children for literacy, employed the phenomenological design, one of the qualitative research methods. In the phenomenological design, participants' experiences about any event are defined (Creswell, 2007). In the current study, pre-school teachers' individual perceptions of the works directed to the preparation of children for literacy and the meanings they assign to them were investigated.

2.1 Study Group

The current study, employing a qualitative research method, was conducted with the participation of 18 pre-school teachers working in pre-school institutions affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in the city of Kars. Of the participating teachers, 17 are females and 1 is male. The participating teachers' length of service varies between 1 year and 7 years. Twelve of the teachers hold a graduate degree from four-year pre-school teacher education program, 4 of them hold an associate's degree and 2 of them are graduates of the department of child development in an open university. The age of the teachers ranges from 24 to 36.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

The data of the current study were collected with a semi-structured interview form and an observation chart developed by the researcher. To this end, the interview questions and observation chart developed by the researcher were submitted to the review of experts on the issue. The semi-structured interview form is made up of two parts. In the first part, there are questions to elicit the demographics of the pre-school teachers. In the second part, there are questions aiming to elicit the participants' opinions about the skills necessary to prepare children for literacy, their practices and problems they experience during the process. Furthermore, an observation chart was used to determine the opportunities provided by the teachers for children in their classes to enhance children's literacy preparation skills. Observations made by the researcher in different times in the classrooms were recorded through the observation chart.

2.3 Data Analysis

In the analysis of the data, the descriptive analysis technique was used. Findings were organized and described on the basis of pre-determined themes. Then, interpretations were made based on these descriptions. The obtained data were separately coded and analyzed by two researchers. Common decisions were reached through the comparison of these analyses.

3. Findings

In this section of the study, findings obtained from the interviews conducted with the pre-school teachers and findings obtained from the classroom observations of the teachers' activities to prepare students for literacy are presented.

3.1 Findings Obtained from the Interviews Conducted with the Pre-school Teachers

In this section of the study, findings related to the pre-school teachers' opinions about preparation for literacy, relevant practices and problems they experience during the process are presented.

Table 1: Activities done by the teachers within the context of preparation for literacy

Activities directed to phonemic awareness skill	
Recognizing the words starting with the same phoneme	14
Recognizing the words ending with the same phoneme	10
Recognizing and distinguishing rhythmic words	9
Producing sounds similar to the target sound	7
Pronouncing the initial phonemes of words	7
Activities directed to supporting writing skill	
Drawing activities (straight, curved, dashed, continuous lines)	18
Painting activities	16
Paper cutting, folding and sticking	10
Recognizing the direction of writing (from left to right, from top to bottom)	8
Holding the pencil properly	7
Activities directed to developing vocabulary	
Concept teaching	12
Encouraging students to use new words in their daily lives	7
Knowing the number of sentences in a sentence	1
Knowing the number of syllables in a word	1
Activities directed to developing alphabet knowledge	
Distinguishing figures, letters and numbers	2
Recognizing capital and lower-case letters	2
Activities directed to visual perception skill	
Interpreting pictures	10
Knowing similarities and differences	7
Activities directed to listening and speaking skills	
Reading book	13
Expressing feelings and opinions	10

As can be seen in Table 1, the pre-school teachers stated that they had mostly conducted activities directed to developing writing skill and phonemic recognition skill. Activities done to promote alphabet knowledge seem to be the least frequently performed activities during the literacy preparation process. The opinions expressed by the seventh participant about this issue are as follows:

"I am getting my students to do drawing activities. Curved, straight, dashed and continuous lines etc. Moreover, there are some activities to strengthen their fingers. From time to time, we play games of finding the initial sound of words."

Table 2: Methods used in activities conducted to prepare for literacy

Completing activity books	16
Reading and narrating books	13
Drama (acting out, role playing, dramatization)	8
Game	7
Music	4

As can be seen in Table 2, the pre-school teachers have frequently used the book reading and completion methods while conducting literacy preparation activities. The opinions expressed by the third participant are as follows:

"I mostly explain them what do to and how to do before getting them engaged in an activity. I demonstrate an example and then let them do. As we do all these in activity books, we can call it "book using"."

Table 3: Places where activities to prepare for literacy are conducted

At the desk	16
In an empty area in the class	10
Learning centers (Book center, arts center)	7
Outdoor	1

As can be seen in Table 3, activities to prepare for literacy are mostly conducted at the desk. Only one teacher stated that he/she conducts some activities in the school garden. The opinions expressed by the twelfth participant about this issue are as follows.

"We are doing the activities at desks. As these activities require pencils, papers, paints or books, desks seem to be the best places. Moreover, we form a circle in the middle of the class. It is also a good place as these activities are performed while reading books."

Table 4: Physical arrangements made in the class for literacy preparation works

Physical arrangement is made	
Yes	12
No	6
Arrangements made	
Hanging visuals	14
Establishing a book center	13
Offering written materials	12

As can be seen in Table 4, most of the pre-school teachers stated that they make some arrangements such as hanging visuals around, establishing a book center and offering written materials to prepare children for literacy. The opinions expressed by the 14th participant about the issue as follows:

"Yes, I am making. For example, I am hanging animal and plant pictures related to the letters of the alphabet. I am writing their names under the pictures. Or, I keep the

alphabet cards we used while doing phonetic activities hung in the class throughout that week. Or I stick children's names on their lockers."

Table 5: Materials used in the activities to prepare children for literacy

Activity books, worksheets	18
Paints	18
Pencils	17
Play dough	13
Board	7
Alphabet cards	7
Children's picture books	7
Lego	6

As can be seen in Table 5, the materials most used in activities done to prepare children for literacy are paints and pencils. The other materials aside from the materials used for writing and drawing seem to have used relatively less. The opinions expressed by the 6th participants about this issue are as follows:

"I mostly use activity books, crayons, finger paint, pencils, books and play dough."

Table 6: Frequency of conducting activities to prepare children for literacy

At least once a week	12
Once in every two weeks	3
Twice a month	2
Once a month	1

As can be seen in Table 6, few of the teachers make very little use of literacy preparation activities (once or twice a month). The opinions expressed by the 16th participant about this issue are as follows.

"I cannot include them much because children do not like doing activity books. Moreover, I do not see them much necessary before elementary school. In the coming years, they will do a lot of such activities; thus, there is now no need to introduce them to such activities."

Table 7: Children' responses to activities done to prepare them for literacy

Responses	
Getting quickly bored	13
Not finding interesting	10
Not enjoying	8
Not focusing attention	7
Psycho-motor challenges	4
Following instructions	3
Causes	
Activities in the book are boring	14
Activities in the book last too long	9
Inadequate level of readiness	7

As can be seen in Table 7, the number of the teachers stating that the children negatively responded to the activities done to prepare them for literacy (getting bored, lack of interest, not enjoying, psychomotor challenges) is higher than the number of teachers stating that the children positively responded to these activities (focusing attention, following instructions). The opinions expressed by the 4th participant about this issue are as follows.

“As the children do not enjoy such activities, they complete them without paying much attention. They are always distracting their own and friends' attention by playing with their crayons. Or they always want to go to the toilet. This process is much more challenging for children with weak finger muscles. They always need help and warning. This is, of course very difficult, in a classroom of 20 students.”

Table 8: The teachers' self-efficacy perception of preparing their students for literacy

Self-confident	
Yes	9
No	9
Causes	
Shortcomings encountered during the undergraduate education	8
Lack of in-service training	6

As can be seen in Table 8, half of the pre-school teachers stated that they do not feel self-confident in preparing their students for literacy by emphasizing the deficiencies in their undergraduate education and in-service training programs offered to them. The opinions expressed by the 7th participant about this issue are as follows.

“I am not adequate because I experience great difficulty in finding activity. I try to make use of the internet, but there are always the same activities. I do not remember whether I took any course during my university education about this issue but I haven't participated in any seminar or training about this. I wish I had more opportunities to train myself on this issue.”

Table 9: Problems experienced during the process of preparing for literacy

Parents' wrong expectations	15
Inadequate psycho-motor development of children	10
Lack of interest on the part of students	7
Difficulty in attaining materials	6

As can be seen in Table 9, the teachers experience the highest number of problems with the parents of children during the process of preparing for literacy. In this regard, the teachers emphasized parents' wrong expectations related to writing teaching, letter teaching, number, summing and subtracting teaching and then the problems related to children's level of readiness. The opinions expressed by the 6th participant on this issue are as follows.

“Parents are always asking to learn what their children are doing. Though I often tell them that there is no need to hurry, that they will learn everything in elementary school, parents are always prone to compare their children with other children.”

In addition to the interviews conducted with the participating pre-school teachers, classroom observations made about the literacy preparation activities were also used as the data source. In the classrooms of five pre-school participants, observations were made for 6 weeks about the literacy preparation activities. Findings obtained from these observations are presented below.

3.2 Findings obtained from the classroom observations made about literacy preparation activities

In the observations made about the activities conducted to prepare children for literacy, activity types, methods used, the place where the activity was done, physical arrangements, tools and equipment, children's responses and problems experienced were the focus of the observations. The findings obtained from the observations revealed that the pre-school teachers did drawing activities (5 teachers) and phonetic awareness activities (4 teachers) relatively more than the others. Some teachers also did vocabulary development activities (2 teachers) and visual perceptions development activities (2 teachers). When the methods used by the pre-school teachers to prepare children for literacy were examined, it was found that they mostly used the methods of book reading and explaining the activity with oral instruction. Acting out and playing games are the other methods used by the pre-school teachers. The observations also revealed that the observations made about the activities done to prepare children for literacy were mostly conducted at desks and that learning centers were not used effectively. The observations also revealed that the only arrangements made by the pre-school teachers within the context of preparing for literacy were desk arrangements and materials provision. Majority of the teachers participating in the study were found to have used paints, coloring books, pencils, play dough, activity books and children's picture books during the activities to prepare children for literacy. Moreover, picture cards, scissors, glue, colorful papers and alphabet letters were the other materials used.

4. Discussion, Results and Suggestions

In the current study, exploring pre-school teachers' competences related to conducting works directed to preparing children for literacy, the data obtained from the interviews conducted with the participating teachers and the data obtained from the classroom observations made about the activities conducted to prepare children for literacy were evaluated together. When the activities conducted by the participating pre-school teachers to prepare children for literacy were examined, it was found that they mostly conducted activities directed to promoting phonemic awareness and writing skills. The observations also revealed that the teachers mostly used drawing activities and phonemic awareness activities; similar findings have also been reported in the relevant

literature. In a study by Dönmezler (2016) investigating the pre-school activities conducted to prepare children for literacy on the basis of the teachers' opinions, it was found that the teachers mostly used photocopies, books and drawing activities. Taşkın, Katrançı and Uygun (2014) investigated the teachers' opinions about the works conducted to prepare children for literacy in the pre-school period and found that the teachers mostly used drawing activities, concept teaching and phonemic activities and they used letter-based activities relatively less. Arnas et al. (2003) made observations on 70 teachers to investigate the activities they conducted and methods they used and concluded that the teachers mostly preferred book and notebook-based activities to prepare children for literacy. On the other hand, Coşkun and Deniz (2017) attempted to determine the pre-school teachers' practices related to preparation for literacy in America, Texas and concluded that the teachers did activities aiming to develop children's spelling recognition, verbal language, phonemic awareness, word recognition, writing and alphabet knowledge. Preparation for literacy is a comprehensive process including many skills such as phonemic awareness, spelling awareness, vocabulary knowledge, alphabet knowledge, visual perception, listening and speaking. The findings of the current study indicate that the pre-school teachers make limited use of activities to develop children's literacy skills because the teachers seem to have focused on the development of these two skills and to have used limited number of activities even to develop these skills. Teachers are expected to conduct activities apart from the ones they mentioned such as disintegrating sentences into words, disintegrating words into syllables and recognizing the last phoneme of a word within the context of preparing children for literacy. Erdoğan, Özen Altınkaynak and Erdoğan (2013) found that the pre-service teachers conducted activities focusing on the initial sounds of words; yet, very few teachers carried out activities related to recognizing the last phoneme of a word, rhythmic words, disintegrating sentences into words and disintegrating words into syllables.

Similarly, activities focusing on the use of written language such as recognizing units making up writing (text, sentence, word, letter), title and author, speaking about the functions of writing, manipulating objects (carrying from one container to another), holding scissors and drawing attention to differences between writing and picture are important activities ignored by teachers to a great extent. Very few of the teachers participating in the current study stated that they conducted activities directed to developing alphabet knowledge. In the pre-school period, alphabet knowledge refers to letter recognition rather than teaching letters. That is, it represents distinguishing letters from the other written language and capital letters and lower-case letters. As very few teachers conducted activities to develop this skill, it may be thought that they do not have much information about this issue. Moreover, lack of activities such as hand-eye coordination, figure-ground distinguishing, stability of figure, location in a place, spatial relationships to support children's visual perceptions during the pre-school period and lack of student-centered activities such as visual presentations and visual reading indicate that the pre-school teachers load limited meaning to literacy preparation activities.

Majority of the teachers participating in the current study stated that they prefer activity book completion, book reading and narrating methods to promote literacy preparation skills. These results show that the pre-school teachers use not many methods and techniques during the process of preparing for literacy. This finding is also supported by the classroom observations revealing that the teachers used teacher-centered methods and techniques. However, according to Sandall and Schwartz (2008), teachers' providing quality literacy experiences to encourage students to develop their literacy and using literacy as both a means and an end by integrating it with music, arts, science, play, physical movement and drama are of great importance. Bochner, Outhred and Pieterse (2001), Coşkun and Deniz (2017), Lynch (2009) reported that teachers do not have much information about the methods and techniques to be used in preparing students for literacy and employ limited number of methods and techniques. Majority of the participating teachers did not use play to support literacy preparation skills, which leads us to think that the teachers do not make effective use of play as an instructional method. However, play is one of the most effective instructional methods to be used in the pre-school period.

Another sub-problem of the current study focused on the environments where activities directed to preparing children for literacy. Majority of the participating teachers stated that they conducted activities at desks; only one teacher stated that he/she also used outdoor places to conduct activities. During the observations made in the current study, it was found that these activities were performed at desks and learning centers were not used effectively. Conducting activities directed to preparing students for literacy only at desks supports, the finding that the teachers load limited meaning to activities conducted to prepare children for literacy. However, activities to prepare children for literacy can be enjoyably conducted in different informal learning environments such as learning centers, school gardens, museums and parks.

The participating teachers were asked whether they made physical arrangements in their classes for activities to prepare children for literacy. The pre-school teachers stated that they made physical arrangements such as establishing book centers, hanging visuals and placing written materials. However, as a result of the classroom observations, it was concluded that the pre-school teachers did not make any physical arrangements but desk arrangement and provision of materials within the context of preparation for literacy. According to Morrow (2007), "early literacy centers" should be one of the focal points of classrooms in the pre-school period. It is important to establish a special area having materials to support reading and writing skills (alphabet knowledge, phonic awareness and vocabulary) in these centers. Moreover, when the relevant literature is reviewed, it is seen that establishing a center including written materials and raising students' awareness of literacy through activities to be conducted and materials to be used in these centers considerably contribute to the development of children's literacy skills (Baroody and Diamond, 2014; Fogo, 2008; Morrow and Gambrell, 2005; Patterson, 2002; Üstün, 2007). The teachers' not establishing new centers to support the development of literacy skills, not updating classroom libraries

and effectively using written instructions may indicate that they ignore the effect of physical environment on literacy preparation skills.

Majority of the participating teachers stated that they used activity books, worksheets, paints, pencils and play dough for their literacy preparation activities. According to Machado (2009), it is of great importance to have materials supporting writing and pre-writing skills (board, books, paints, cards, vocabulary box, letters of the alphabet, chalks, scissors, glue, eraser, moulds, notebook, pencil sharpener, sticks, baskets, hole puncher, ink), reading and pre-reading materials (books made by children, audio-visual books, puzzle cards, alphabet cards on which children's names are written, story cards), materials supporting speaking skills (puppet, puppet stage, flannel board) and materials supporting audio-visual perception skills (overhead projector, cassettes, CD/DVD players, headphones, TV, computer, printer and video camera) in pre-school classrooms. In a study conducted by Farver, Xu, Lonigan and Eppe (2013), a positive correlation was found between the existence of tools and equipment to promote literacy and children's linguistic skills and spelling knowledge. The participating teachers' not using different types of materials in their activities may indicate that they ignore the effect of material on preparing students for literacy.

Within the context of another sub-problem of the current study, the participating teachers were asked their frequency of conducting activities to prepare children for literacy and majority of the teachers stated that they conduct these activities at least once a week. When the teachers were asked what their students' responses to these activities were, they said that there were more negative responses. The teachers stated that their students got easily bored with the activities to prepare them for literacy, did not feel interest in these activities, experienced some difficulties and did not enjoy them. When these findings are evaluated under the light of other findings of the current study, they do not seem to be surprising because both the interviews conducted with the teachers and the classroom observations have revealed that the activities conducted to prepare children for literacy are limited to activities performed at the desk and lacking creativity, physical and mental movement and mostly based on activity books and drawings. When children's developmental characteristics and needs are considered, it seems to be inevitable for children to respond to these activities negatively.

Another sub-problem of the study asked the teachers to explain whether they see themselves competent in conducting activities to prepare children for literacy with their reasons. While half of the teachers stated that they are competent enough, the other half stated that they are not and they pointed to inadequacies in their undergraduate education and lack of in-service training programs. In a study conducted by Bay (2008), similar findings were obtained and the pre-school teachers' self-efficacy scores in relation to activities to prepare children for literacy were found to be high.

The current study finally investigated the problems experienced by the pre-school teachers during the process of preparing children for literacy. The findings obtained from the interviews conducted with the teachers showed that the most frequently experienced problems are related to parents' wrong expectations. The pre-

school teachers stated that parents confuse literacy with literacy preparation activities and they would like teachers to teach letters, which is not suitable for the development level of children at this age. Moreover, the teachers also pointed to problems resulting from psycho-motor deficiencies such as holding the pencil properly, holding the book properly and hand-eye coordination. Dönmezler (2016) also pointed out that parents' desires about literacy and math instruction and their persistence on their desires make teachers' job more difficult.

In short, as a result of the current study it was concluded that the pre-school teachers conduct limited variety of activities within the context of preparing children for literacy, they mostly prefer desks to conduct these activities, they prefer teacher-centered activities and they experience some problems during the process in relation to parents, children and provision of materials. In light of the findings of the current study, the following suggestions can be made: In-service training programs can be planned to develop pre-school teachers about the process of preparing for literacy. Pre-school undergraduate programs can be enhanced by adding required courses to make pre-service teachers more competent in preparing children for literacy or the existing courses can be enhanced with more practice opportunities. Pre-school teachers can organize educational activities, workshops and seminars to inform families about the process of preparation for literacy. The current study employed the qualitative design. Future research employing the quantitative design to explore the relationship between teachers' practices directed to preparing children for literacy and children's skills of preparing for literacy can contribute to the literature. The results of the current study can be compared with the results to be obtained from more comprehensive studies exploring different variables.

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